

Ethics and Integrity in Development Management

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 09 February 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Ethics in development management Integrity in development management Corruption in development projects Ethics in sustainable development</p>	<p>This study reviewed the concept of ethics and integrity and how they can be applied in the context of development management. The study found that bureaucracy, abuse of political power and low priority for quality assurance are some of the major challenges facing ethics and integrity in development management. Moreover, the study found that effective auditing and oversight, participatory budgeting, transparency and proportionate and dissuasive sanctions are some of the ways that can be used to ensure ethics and integrity in the development management.</p>

1. Background to ethics and integrity

1.1 Ethics

Ethics refers to well-founded standards of right and wrong, that prescribe what humans ought to do, usually in terms of rights, obligations, benefits to society, fairness, or specific virtues (Rich, 2021). Ethics consists of the fundamental issues of practical decision making, and its major concerns include the nature of ultimate value and the standards by which human actions can be judged right or wrong. According to Six, Tankeren & Huberts (2008), ethics refers to those standards that impose the reasonable obligations to refrain from immoral practices such as stealing and fraud. They include standards that enjoin virtues of honesty, compassion, and loyalty. Ethics also means the continuous effort of studying our own moral beliefs and our moral conduct, and striving to ensure that we, and the institutions we help to shape, live up to standards that are reasonable and solidly-based (Shacklock & Lewis, 2007).

1.2 Integrity

Integrity is the practice or quality of being honest and showing a consistent and uncompromising adherence to strong moral and ethical principles and values (Huberts, 2018). In ethics, integrity is regarded as the honesty and truthfulness or accuracy of one's actions. As Dunn (2009) explains, integrity is the inner sense of "wholeness" deriving from qualities such as honesty and consistency of character. In other words, integrity is based upon an internally consistent framework of moral actions, beliefs, methods, measures, and principles.

2. Background to development management

2.1 Meaning of development management

Development management is the strategic planning, administration and controlling of a project during its development life cycle, from project planning through to completion and project exit. According to Thomas (2000, p. 106), development management can be thought of in terms of positive linkages between development, capacity building and learning in individual, organizational, institutional and societal levels. On the other hand, Wallace (2000) notes that development management means evaluating change from the present situation into a better future situation. It is the process of improving, building and innovating in order to ensure better quality of life for the present people without jeopardizing those of the future. In light of these definitions, it can be concluded that development management is a process of conducting development in a systematic way to improve the quality of life of the people. It includes the management of the specific tasks involved in social and economic development interventions.

2.2 Emergence of development management

The term "development management" came into use in the 1950s to represent those aspects of public management and the changes in public

management, which were needed to carry out policies, projects, and programs to improve social and economic conditions. After the second world war, countries achieved independence and political autonomy. The new status gave promise of freedom, liberty and self-determination in political systems of representative democracy. The term was therefore coined to refer to the process of pro-actively managing development, especially in the local areas, and guiding organizations towards the achievement of progressive political, economic and social objectives (Chakrabarty & Chand, 2021).

2.3 Components of development management

The first element of development management is capacity building by developing and strengthening processes and resources that organizations and communities need to facilitate management of development process (Wallace, 2000). Technical assistance is another element of development management involving provision of targeted support to organizations require to address the development needs. The third component of development management is the leadership and participation, through effective team and stakeholder engagements (Thomas, 2000). The fourth component is the decentralization and empowerment where development processes are moved away from the main administrative authorities to give power to the locals.

2.4 Benefits of development management

Development management helps organizations and countries to achieve development goals and objectives with reduced cost. Through development management, organizations involved in the development process are able to balance expenditure and expenditure other on important requirements of development projects. It enables organizations and countries to implement their projects and programs cost effectively and promote judicious management of various aspects of development programs. According to Haq & Zafarulla (2006), development management helps the managers engaged in development process to apply a systemic approach to maximize efficiency and performance of development programs and projects. Moreover, development management helps to achieve the goal of absolute, collaborative, adaptive, tacit and empowerment in the development process. In general, development management provides the foundation for the character and pace of economic and social development.

2.5 Prerequisites for good development management

Studies have found that intra and intra-sectoral coordination is essential for smooth implementation of development activities. Chakrabarty & Chand (2021) assert that for the effective management of development projects or programs, the development management must have a climate of healthy inter-sectoral coordination. Similarly, good governance has been found to facilitate faster development process. According to the United

Nations (2020), the features of good governance include consensus orientation, participation, accountability, transparency, responsiveness, equity and inclusiveness. Development management needs to use good governance as a tool for effective implementation of development activities to achieve development goals. Moreover, effective leadership can integrate and utilize scarce resources for the accomplishment of institutional goal. Effective leadership helps create an environment where sustained economic growth becomes achievable. On the other hand, convergence of activities helps curtail duplication and overlapping of activities. In addition, decentralization enables development agencies to be more sensitive and responsive to local priorities and needs, allocate resources effectively and be more accountable to the people.

3. Ethics and Integrity in development management

3.1 Why ethics and integrity in development management?

It is observed that a gigantic share of government resources to the development agencies involved in the implementation of various projects in the country. Judicious allocation of such resources is critical to development management. Any unbalanced allocation and use of resources has implications on the outcomes of developmental projects. Therefore, the important role of ethics and integrity is to see that the resources are allocated properly on various aspects of development. Ethics and integrity helps to enhance accountability and transparency of the development agencies and creates a greater public awareness of the development processes. According to Enste & Christina (2017), ethics and integrity principles provide the foundation for organization's values, aspirations and patterns of thought and conduct throughout the development process. Integrating ethics and integrity into day-to-day operations of an organizations help prevent damaging ethical lapses while endorsing a code of moral standard for the organizations. Ethics and integrity in management give life to an organization's values, and create an environment that supports ethically sound behavior and a sense of shared accountability among employees involved in the development process. Ethical values shape the design of organizational systems, and the decision-making process used by individuals and groups in the development agencies. Ethics and integrity also provide a common frame of reference and serve as a unifying force across different functions and lines of operations.

3.2 Dimensions of ethics and integrity in development management

Personal ethics and integrity forms an important dimension of ethics and integrity in development management. Personal ethics reflect general expectations of any person in any organization, acting in any capacity. Some of the principles of personal ethics include concern for the well-being of others, respect for the autonomy of others, trustworthiness & honesty, willing compliance with the law, basic justice, being fair, refusing to take unfair advantage, adhering to the golden rule, doing good, preventing harm and honoring obligations (Kipnis & South, 2000). Professional ethics and integrity is another dimension of ethics and integrity in the development management. Professionals have codes of ethics that prescribe required behaviors within the context of the professional practice in the development processes. According to Kipnis & South (2000), the written codes provide rules of conduct and standards of behavior based on the principles of professionalism. The principles include objectivity, impartiality, openness, full information disclosure, efficient communication, confidentiality; due diligence; fidelity to professional responsibility and avoiding conflict of interest.

3.3 Challenges facing ethics and integrity in development management

The role of bureaucratic domination as the main tool of development has always been questioned. Bureaucracy is an efficient instrument with which administrative policies are implemented (Eme, Samuel & Chidubem, 2017). In the case of development projects, there are always allegations of mismanagement by the political bureaucrats. This creates opportunities for more unethical practices in the overall development of the state. On the other hand, political incapability and politicization of the development process is one of the biggest problems facing developing countries. Due to the weakness of both the political parties and the interest groups, the right problems are not represented. Its effect can be seen in the policy, where political systems fail to administer proper implementation of developmental policies.

Low priority for quality assurance, monitoring and evaluation prevent successful implementation of development programs. At the same time, the extent to which the development projects are being implemented are not properly evaluated. This leads to shoddy and poor workmanship on the development projects. The result is projects with poor quality that can collapse within a few years. Such projects are a source of danger to their users. Furthermore, in most state systems, the government has a huge amount of power in its hands so that it can guide the development process in the right way. However, in reality, politically influential people abuse their political power and control to influence the administration of development programs (Onuche, 2018). Political parties and senior government officials in many cases appoint people of their choice in the management of national projects.

3.4 Manifestations of the challenges facing ethics and integrity in development management

Lack of personal and professional ethics is some of the major manifestations of the challenges facing ethics and integrity in the development management. The lack of professional ethics is a particular issue, as many countries require different amounts of time and resources to develop or change their ethics and professional standards. Moreover, lack of transparency and a lack of control by supervisory institutions poses a unique challenge to implementation of ethics and integrity in the development process. Furthermore, insufficient, deficient and incomplete legislation, where laws are interpreted in different ways allow malfunctioning of the processes of development management. Little decisional power regarding penalizing unethical characterizes environments that are conducive for unethical conducts in development process.

Another major manifestation is the administrative corruption, which leads to diversion of resources that are otherwise meant for development processes (Anders, 2019). Ineffective sanctioning of corruption by development agencies increases the possibility of recurrent corruptive actions of those involved and creating a strong room for others to join in the corruption malpractices. In most cases, corruption is commonly equated with bribery, where an illegal payment is made to a government official in return for some favor that in the absence of the payment would not have been done (Morris, 2011). Beyond bribery, corruption also includes kickbacks where an illegal payment is made after the service is rendered, usually from a portion of a governmental award. While such acts involve transactions between citizens and government officials, corruption also includes graft, fraud, conflict of interest, influence peddling, cronyism, clientelism and embezzlement, where public officials act to misappropriate public funds or divert their intended use from the development process.

3.5 Effects of the challenges facing ethics and integrity in development management

Challenges of ethics and integrity unnecessarily increase and inflate the size of public investment in the development process, because many items in public expenditure lend themselves to manipulations by high level officials to get bribes. The challenges create a skewed composition of public expenditure, away from needed operations and maintenance of public development projects. Unethical practices limits development in critical social sectors such as health and education. According to Tanzi (1998), these challenges reduce productivity of public investment of the development infrastructure. The result is reduced tax revenue that further limits the government's ability to expand other development projects. Lack of ethics and integrity affects equitable distribution of resources, increases income inequalities, undermines the effectiveness of social welfare programs and ultimately results in lower levels of human development. This undermines long-term socio-economic and political development.

4. Addressing challenges facing ethics and integrity in development management

According to Myint (2000), public sector reforms focusing on improving management of public resources and strengthening the role of auditing and oversight agencies have in many countries achieved greater impact on promoting ethics and integrity in the development processes. One such reform is the disclosure of budget information, to prevent mismanagement of resources meant for development projects. Another form is promoting participatory budgeting where local communities comment on budgets for development projects.

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Similarly, promoting transparency ensures institutional openness, freedom of the media and access to information (Bhargava, 2012). Access to information increases the responsiveness of development agencies, while simultaneously having a positive effect on the levels of public involvement in development process. Moreover, empowering citizens to demand for anti-corruption and hold the government accountable helps to build mutual trust between citizens and government. Community-monitoring initiatives contribute to the detection of corruption, reduced leakages of development funds and improve the quality of public services. In addition, prevention mechanisms often start with rules that prohibit certain types of conduct. Rules not only include legal prohibitions against unethical conducts but also codes of conduct and ethics for public officials (Rose-Ackerman, 1997). Enforcement of ethics and integrity rules and codes of conduct promotes adherence to the norms in the public sector by creating an environment for compliance. Moreover, effective, proportionate and dissuasive sanctions and measures that compensate victims of unethical conducts, including the government, can deter misconduct and ensure judicious use of resources in the development process (Zhu, 2012).

6. Conclusion

Development management is important for strategic planning, management and controlling of projects during their development life cycle. However, due to the huge share of government resources to the development agencies, it is critical that mechanisms and frameworks of ethics and integrity are put in place to prevent misuse of the resources meant for the development processes. These, among others, include public sector reforms, efficient public resource management, transparency and public participation, legislations, codes of conduct and penalties for those found guilty of unethical practices in the course of development management.

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References

Anders, G. (2019). *African anti-corruption agencies and the problem of independence*. Washington: Global Integrity.

- Bhargava, V. (2012). *Strategies for Empowering Communities to Demand Good Governance and Seek Increased Effectiveness of Public Service Delivery*. Washington: Partnership for Transparency Fund.
- Chakrabarty, B., & Chand, P. (2021). *Public administration in a globalizing world: theories and practices*. SAGE Publications.
- Dunn, C. (2009). Integrity matters. *International Journal of Leadership Studies*, 5(2), 102-125.
- Eme, O., Samuel, I., & Emmanuel, E. (2017). African Anti-Corruption Agencies: Challenges and Prospects. *Management Studies and Economic Systems*, 3(4), 225-243.
- Enste, D., & Heldman, C. (2017). *Causes and consequences of corruption: An overview of empirical results*, IW-Report, No. 2/2017. Koln: Institut der deutschen Wirtschaft.
- Haq, A. & Zafarulla, H. (2006). *International Development Governance*. London: Taylor and Francis.
- Huberts, L. (2018). Integrity: What it is and Why it is Important. *Public Integrity*, 20(1), 18-532.
- Kipnis, K., & South, D. Personal Values & Professional Ethics. *Journal of Forestry –Washington*, 98(7), 11-14.
- Morris, S. (2011). Forms of corruption. *CESifo DICE report*, 9(2), 10-14.
- Myint, U. (2000). Corruption: Causes, consequences and cures. *Asia pacific development journal*, 7(2), 33-58.
- Onuche, S. (2018). Examination of the Challenges on the Fight Against Corruption in Nigeria (online).
- Rich, K. L. (2016). *Introduction to ethics. Nursing ethics: Across the curriculum and into practice*. London: Jones and Bartlett
- Rose-Ackerman, S. (1997). Corruption: Causes, consequences and cures. *Trends in Organized Crime*, 3(1), 109-111
- Shacklock, A., & Lewis, M. (2007). *Leading with Integrity: a fundamental principle of integrity and good governance*. In Brisbane: World Ethics Forum.
- Six, F., Tankeren, M., & Huberts, L. (2008, September). *What works in ethics and integrity management: where do we stand today*. In Paper EGPA conference, Rotterdam.
- Tanzi, V. (1998). Corruption around the world: Causes, consequences, scope, and cures. *Staff papers*, 45(4), 559-594.
- Thomas, A. (2000). What makes good development management? In Wallace, T. (2000). *Development and Management*. London: Oxfam Publication.
- United Nations. (2020). Principles of good governance. Author.
- Wallace, T. (2000). *Development and Management*. London: Oxfam Publication.
- Zhu, J. (2012). Do severe penalties deter corruption? A game-theoretic analysis of the Chinese case. *China Review*, 12(2), 1-32.